

Research

Accelerated Carbonation Of Concrete For Carbon Capture, Utilization, And Storage (Ccus): A Critical Analysis Of Techniques And Their Impact On Performance

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Abstract: The construction industry faces a significant challenge in reducing its carbon footprint. Accelerated carbonation, a process that converts calcium hydroxide ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$) into calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) within concrete through controlled CO_2 exposure, offers a promising avenue for carbon capture, utilization, and storage (CCUS). This paper critically analyzes various accelerated carbonation techniques, their impact on the mechanical properties and durability of concrete, and their potential role in sustainable construction practices.

Keywords: Carbonation, service life, durability, microstructure of concrete.

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1.INTRODUCTION

Carbonation is known as a neutralizing process, a chemical reaction of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ and calcium–silicate–hydrate (C–S–H) with CO_2 to form CaCO_3 and water. Carbonation reduces the hydroxide concentration in the pore solution, destroying the passivity of the embedded reinforcement bars. The traditional way of determining the depth of carbonation is to spray phenolphthalein indicator onto the surface of a freshly split concrete prism. The solution is a colorless base indicator, which turns purple when the pH is above 9. Past evidence has shown that a partially carbonated zone exists where pH is difficult to detect using the phenolphthalein indicator. Concrete production contributes heavily to global CO_2 emissions, primarily due to cement manufacturing. Accelerated carbonation presents a unique opportunity to mitigate these emissions by sequestering CO_2 within concrete structures. This study examines the effectiveness of various accelerated carbonation techniques while critically assessing their potential benefits and limitations for the construction industry.

2. FUNDAMENTAL RESEARCH ON CARBONATION PROCESS

2.1 Mechanism and Kinetics

The process of carbonation of concrete is a combination of various physical and chemical processes. The carbon dioxide is present in ambient atmosphere or internal air of buildings. The instrumental mechanism of carbonation is the reaction of diffused CO_2 with calcium hydroxide. The final products of this reaction are CaCO_3 and water a major hydration product in Portland cement:

(1) The physicochemical processes involved in carbonation are: (Thiery et al. 2007)

(2) The diffusion of CO_2 in the gaseous phase of the concrete pores.

(3) The dissolution of CO_2 in the pore water as carbonic acid.

(4) Dissociation of CO_2 as H_2CO^3 and CO_3^{2-} ions.

(5) The dissolution of solid $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$.

(6) Releasing of calcium Ca^{2+} and hydroxyl OH^- ions.

(7) And the precipitation of CO_3^{2-} , forming CaCO_3

These intermediate reactions are represented in the following overall chemical reaction given in equation

This exothermic reaction typically occurs slowly in natural environments. However, various methods can accelerate the process significantly.

3. DISCUSSION: EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES AND PREDICTION MODELS FOR DIFFERENT INFLUENCING FACTORS

A need to review the already existing findings and facts evolved, to help in paving the way for further investigations. So, the effects of the several factors affecting carbonation and environmental loading which affect the service life of concrete structures are described in detail. The models proposed and issues of uncertainty in prediction and evaluation of carbonation

propagation is also discussed in this section.

3.1 Effect of Curing Condition

The influence of curing on concrete carbonation can be in terms of the type of curing and in terms of initial curing period. Conclusions drawn upon Impact of curing may also be different for natural long-term carbonation with site-curing and accelerated carbonation with laboratory-controlled curing. In a critical review by (Ekolu 2016), the author points out that the studies on effects of different curing methods on natural carbonation of concrete in real structures are

very rare. Different methods of curing have been studied in the laboratory including heat curing (Neville 1995; Ekolu 2006; T. Y. Lo et al. 2016), air curing, moist curing (Neville 1995; Y. Lo and Lee 2002; Aprianti et al. 2016; Balayssac et al. 1995) and use of curing compounds (Neville 1995; Xue et al. 2015).

In an experimental study, (Y. Lo and Lee 2002) prepared three different normal weight concrete grades A, B and C with water-cement ratios of 0.38, 0.46 and 0.54, respectively, to study the effects of initial curing method on the depth of carbonation. The details of 3 mixes are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Mix Proportion Per Cubic Meter of Concrete

Properties	Mix A	Mix C	Mix C
w/c Ratio	0.38	0.46	0.54
OPC(kg)	450	450	450
20 mm granite aggregate (kg)	665	655	645
10 mm granite aggregate (kg)	530	515	510
Rock fines (kg)	535	525	515
Superplasticizer (ml)	2400	0	0

For each grade, 8cubes of 100×100 mm²dimension and 8 units of 100Ø×200 mm high cylinders were cast and stored in water at 27 ± 3°. After 28 days, the cubes were tested for compressive strength. The cylinders were taken out from the carbonation chamber after 30, 60, and 90 days and were split in a tensile splitting test. The transverse exposed surfaces were cleaned and tested for carbonation depth using phenolphthalein indicator and a Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy. It was observed that the carbonation depth increases with w/c ratio, the age of concrete and the initial curing period. This difference in carbonation depths between air cured and water cured samples were very small with moist curing giving slightly lower carbonation depth. The discrepancy in the carbonation depth measured by IR for both air- and water-cured conditions reduced over time. Samples cured in water for 28 days became carbonated to only 53% of the level for air-cured samples but then increased to 78% after the three-month period. It is also to be noted that 28-days strengths of moist cured samples were slightly higher. In a critical review on effect of curing on long-term natural carbonation of concrete, cited the long-term experimental studies by CSIR and highlighted the fact that, none of the curing regimes caused a change of strength class of a given mixture or any change in their respective carbonation behaviors under outdoor exposure, refer table 2. In this study, it was observed that, for each strength class, the carbonation depths at later ages differ by about ±2 mm, regardless of the curing regime. Statistical analysis was conducted to assess whether the concretes subjected to the different curing regimes exhibited a significant change in carbonation. 95% confidence limit graphs were plotted. The residuals fell within the 95% confidence interval, indicating the absence of statistically significant differences between results of the various curing regimes. It was concluded that it is only if a curing method causes a change in strength class of a mixture, that corresponding carbonation behaviors of the mix can be expected to alter significantly.

Table 2. Results of Carbonation Depth Using Phenolphthalein Test and Infrared Spectroscopic Test

Mix (w/c)	Curing type	Strength (MPa)	Carbonation depth (mm) Phenolphthalein P infrared spectrum(I)		
			1	2	3
Age (month)			1	2	3
A (0.38)	Air	66	1 (1.5)	3.5 (4.5)	5 (6)
	Water	78	0.5 (1)	1.5 (3)	3 (4.5)
B (0.46)	Air	44	1.5 (3)	4 (6)	7 (8)
	Water	63	1 (3)	2.5 (4.5)	5 (6)
C (0.54)	Air	35	3 (4.5)	5.5 (8)	10 (12)
	Water	54	1.5 (3)	4 (6)	8.5 (10)

Table 3. Properties Of Concrete Used By (Balayssac et al. 1995)

Concrete	Cement	cement content (C) (kg m ⁻³)	Water/Cement	Gravel/Sand	Characteristic Strength (MPa)
B1	CPJ45	300	0.65	1.00	25.1
B2	CPJ45	340	0.61	1.13	32.6
B3	CPJ45	380	0.53	1.13	37.8
B4	CPJ45	420	0.48	1.15	43.5
-	CPA55	250	0.73	0.92	26.4
-	CPA55	280	0.65	0.94	30.0
-	CPA55	300	0.59	0.96	35.0
-	CPA55	350	0.54	1.04	41.8
-	CLK45	340	0.61	1.17	24.9
-	CLK45	400	0.50	1.15	31.9

The initial curing period of concrete plays a significant role in carbonation of concrete. When curing is conducted for the proper time, the susceptibility of concrete to carbonation reduces. The purpose of curing is to maintain a required range of moisture and temperature.

An experimental study was conducted by (Balayssac et al. 1995) using concrete mixes of a range of strength from 25 to 40 MPa. All mixes provided the same slump (8 cm). Cement content, w/c ratios and 28-day strengths are given in Table 3 and Oxide composition, and physical properties of cement are given in Table 4.

Table 4. Oxide Composition And Physical Properties Of Cement Used In (Balayssac et al. 1995)

Cement	CPJ45	CPA55	CLK45
SiO₂	26.2	20.1	30.3
Al₂O₃	3.1	5.4	11.5
Fe₂O₃	3.2	3.2	-
CaO	58.9	63.2	45.2
MgO	0.6	2.2	4.75
SO₃	2.6	2.3	2.9
K₂O	-	1.22	0.76
Na₂O	-	-	0.6
Ss(m³kg⁻¹)	350	370	385
Density	3.01	3.15	2.93

After demolding at one day, the test samples were stored in a controlled environment (20°C and 60% relative humidity) or kept in water up to 3 or 28 days, before exposure to the environment (with a CO₂ content of 0.03%), for up to 18 months. Cylinders with 11 cm diameter and 10 cm height were used in this study whose ends were sawn after demolding. Also, after curing the lateral surfaces were covered with aluminum sheets. After an appointed period (90, 180, 360 and 540 days) three test samples were split to obtain a break without wet sawing. The carbonated depth was measured using phenolphthalein solution. Carbonation depth decreased with increase in cement content for any curing time, (also 28-day strength). For the concrete with a cement content of 350 kg m⁻³, increasing the period of curing from 1 days to 28 days caused the reduction of the carbonation depth to half. When the curing period was increased from 1 to 3 days, there was a rapid decrease in carbonation depth followed by slower variations. It is to be noted if cement content is too low, carbonation depth is still high despite good curing. Also, curing effects depend on cement type. Increasing curing period does not have the same effect, for the same cement content, on the concrete of Portland Cement as on the concrete of slag cement. One day curing was found to be insufficient for all the concretes regardless of the cement content. In conclusion, curing period of 3 days is sufficient for concretes with a cement content higher than 380 kg m⁻³ for good carbonation resistance. Detailed data on carbonation depths obtained are given in Table 5.

Table 5. Carbonation Depths Observed In (Balayssac et al. 1995)

Concrete	Properties	Curing Period	Age(day)			
			90	180	360	540
B1	Cement content=300 kg m ⁻³ W/C=0.65 28-day strength=25.1 MPa	1 day	6.5	11	13	15
		3 day	4	6	9.5	13
		28 day	3	5	6	9
B2	Cement content=340 kg m ⁻³ W/C=0.61 28-day strength=32.6 MPa	1 day	5.5	10	12	13
		3 day	3.5	5	6	8
		28 day	2.5	4	4.5	6
B3	Cement content=380 kg m ⁻³ w/c=0.53 28-day strength=37.8 MPa	1 day	4.5	9	10	11.5
		3 day	3	5	5.5	7
		28 day	2	3.5	4	5
B4	Cement content=420 kg m ⁻³ w/c=0.48 28-day strength=43.8 MPa	1 day	4	7.5	8.5	9.5
		3 day	2.5	4	3.5	4
		28 day	1.5	3	3	3.5

3.2 Ambient Temperature and Thermal Properties

Small variations in temperature have little effect on carbonation. High temperature increases the carbonation rate unless drying overcomes the temperature effect. It also affects the passivity of steel rebars in reinforced concrete. Although, the thermal conductivity of concrete is a well-researched topic because of its importance for fire resistant design and energy conservation, its variation during carbonation of cement materials has not been studied to a good extent. The heat of hydration of concrete or occurrence of temperature gradient may lead to cracks in a concrete structure Propagation of cracks increases the susceptibility of concrete to carbonation.

3.2.1 Effects of Ambient Temperature on Passivity Capacity of Reinforcement

Jiezhen (Hu et al. 2015) studied the coupled effect of temperature and carbonation on the corrosion of reinforcement by using open circuit method (OCP), the electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and the potential-dynamic polarization (PP) in the simulated concrete pore solutions (SPSs). The OCP was used to evaluate corrosion tendency of rebar in SPSs, the passivation film of the rebars was evaluated by using EIS and the corrosion current or dissolution velocity of the passivated surface of the rebars was evaluated using potentiodynamic polarization measurements. Following observations were made:

- *The Effect of Temperature and pH on the OCP:* The rebars were found to be prone to corrosion in higher temperature and lower pH SPSs. The corrosion of rebar was high at the pH = 9.6 and 318K SPSs. The rebars had the best corrosion-resistance at the pH= 10.6 and 318K temperature of SPSs.
- *The Effect of Temperature and pH on the Passivation Film of Rebar:* The rebars were found to have greater capacity of passivity at a lower temperature. Moderate pH value (11.6) SPSs was found to be favorable for passivation layer.
- *The Effect of Temperature and pH on the Corrosion Current of Rebar:* The passive current of rebars in the higher pH value SPSs was bigger than that of rebars in lower pH value SPSs. This means that the dissolution velocity of the passivated

surface is bigger if the pH of the SPSs is very high. Also, the high temperature and high pH environment are favorable for the formation of passivated surface.

In conclusion, the high-temperature environment is favorable for the formation of the passivated surface of rebars in the SPSs. But the dissolution velocity of the passivated surface is higher in the high-temperature SPSs. Also, rebars have a greater capacity of passivity at a lower temperature. The corrosion rate of rebars at higher temperature is smaller in moderate pH value (10.6) SPSs. The rebars suffer from serious corrosion in the pH= 9.6 SPSs at (High) 318K temperature.

For a service life model for Reinforced Concrete, it is very important to monitor the change in the pH of the pore solution. As discussed above, the onset of corrosion as well as the degree of corrosion is highly dependent on pH of pore solution. As per (Papadakis, Fardis, et al. 1991) the pH of carbonated concrete can be written as equation:

$$\text{pH} = 14 + \log \left(2 \times 10^3 \right) \left[\text{Ca} (\text{OH})_2 \right]_{\text{aq}}$$

As per the best knowledge of the authors, most of the models available for service life prediction of reinforced concrete doesn't consider the effect of temperature on passivity of rebars. The threshold value pH for onset of corrosion is dependent upon the temperature.

3.2.2 Effects of Sudden Changes in Temperature

S.K. Roy (Roy et al. 1999) explains that concrete structures which are exposed to the environment, faces not only seasonal and long-term changes in temperature but also face sudden changes due to rain or due to change in temperate during day and night cycle. When there is sudden fall in temperature, the outer concrete surface contracts more than the inside and tensile stress occur at the surface and compressive stress inside. Also, while the temperature rises suddenly, the outer surface of concrete expands more than the inside and compressive stresses develop at the surface and tensile stresses develop inside. This may lead to the formation of microcracks in concrete structures increasing the surface are exposed to CO₂. Leading to an increase in carbonation

3.3 Effects on Thermal Conductivity

There is a good agreement to the fact that carbonation causes a reduction in the total porosity of concrete and alters its pore size distribution. The overall effect is that carbonation tends to increase the thermal conductivity appreciably. (Pham and Prince 2013).

The thermal conductivity of concrete is a function of mix properties, types of aggregates used, as well as moisture status. (Morabito 1989); (Neville 1995) and (Lanciani et al. 1989). Higher w/c ratios give a more porous structure. The pores have low thermal conductivity and heat capacity compared to the other phases present in concrete. More porosity enables a better scope for the influence of moisture content on the heat capacity of concrete. The moisture in any form in concrete, i.e. Chemically bound, physically bound or free water, have higher heat capacity.

The changes in the microstructure and microphysical properties caused by the carbonation of

normalized CEM II mortar were examined in detail by (Pham and Prince 2013). Normalized mortar prepared with French Cement CEM II / BM (V-LL) 32.5 R and standard sand certified in accordance with EN 196-1 were used. The w/c and sand/cement ratios were respectively 0.5 and 3. At the end of the mixing, the mortar was placed in cylindrical molds (Diameter =40mm, height =60mm). The samples were demolded after 24 hours and then cured for 90 days in a humid chamber (20°C, 100% relative humidity). Samples were subjected to accelerated carbonation at 20°C, 65% relative humidity and 20% CO₂ concentration. A Hot Disk Thermal Constants analyzer was used to perform the thermal conductivity test at 20°. A plane Hot Disk sensor was fixed between two pieces of the sample – each one with a plane surface facing the sensor. The hot Disk sensor had a dynamic role. The disc was used both as a heat source and as a dynamic temperature sensor. Electrical current, high enough to increase the temperature of the sensor was passed. The increase in resistance (temperature) was recorded as a function of time. Fig. 1 presents the variation of thermal conductivity during carbonation. The study confirmed that the thermal conductivity increases with increase in carbonation

Fig. 1: Evolution of thermal conductivity with carbonation; Source: (Pham and Prince 2013)

3.4 Carbonation and Porosity of Concrete

As carbonation proceeds from the outer surface into internal portions of concrete, the microstructure is also changed continuously from the outer surface into internal portions of concrete and consequently changing the porosity of the concrete. As CaCO₃ occupies a greater volume than Ca(OH)₂, which when it replaces, the porosity is reduced with the advancement of carbonation (Papadakis et al. 1991b; Burkan Isgor et al. 2004). Higher porosity gives rise to more carbonation, this has been verified experimentally in a study by (Valcuende et al. 2010). Natural carbonation of self-compacting concrete was investigated in this study. Eight different Concretes were used which consisted of four self-compacting concrete (SCC) and four normally vibrated concrete (NVC). The carbonation rate was found to be lower in SCC than NVC. It was attributed to the fact that limestone fines produce less porosity and finer microstructure of concrete. Also, the difference between both types of concrete tended to disappear as their fines content becomes similar.

In a study by Roy (Roy et al. 1999) the relationship between carbonation and nature of the pores in the concrete was studied in detail. Larger pores gave rise to higher carbonation depths. Twenty concrete panels were cast and cured for 28 days and kept in two different locations for 2 years. Upon completion of the process, the median pore diameter was determined Fig. 2 shows that the median pore diameters for the unmolded samples (with large carbonation depth) are greater than those of the molded samples (smaller carbonation depth). The result presented in the figure 2 which compose the carbonation depth with the median pore size and show a higher carbonation depth for increased pore size is also expected since a higher porosity will produce a higher diffusion rate for carbon dioxide. The importance of uniform and well-

compacted concrete is also demonstrated since badly compacted or honeycombed concrete leads to high porosity and rapid carbonation.

The pore blocking due to rain etc. in concrete also influence the carbonation and hence it should also be accounted in a concrete porosity model. The depth profiling of carbonates formed during natural carbonation of mortars with one face exposed directly to rain and opposite face sheltered has been measured and compared. Due to pore blocking by periodic rainwater, the number of carbonates formed on mortars sheltered from rain was found to be generally higher. As expected and explained in (Papadakis et al. 1991a).

Fig 2: Median pore diameter and carbonation depth against concrete samples for molded and unmolded layers, Source: (Roy et al. 1999)

4. CARBONATION OF CONCRETE CONTAINING BLENDED CEMENTS

Blended cements are widespread in use, and different types of cement have very different

microstructural and physical properties. Thus, it is essential to understand the nuances of carbonation properties of different hardened cement paste made up of pozzolana cement, ground granulated blast furnace slag cement etc. The effect of supplementary cementing materials (SCM) on concrete resistance against carbonation and chloride ingress has been studied by

(Papadakis 2000). The silica fume and low and high calcium fly ash were used as SCM. Experimental investigations simulating main deterioration mechanisms in reinforced concrete were carried out. It was observed that the carbonation depth decreases as Aggregate replacement by SCM increases and increases as Cement replacement by SCM increases.

4.1 Carbonation of Cement Containing Fly Ash

It has been reported that the normal dosages of fly ash addition result in the slight increment of the carbonation of concrete whereas in concrete with normal moist-curing periods, carbonation is not affected by the significant amount. Many studies have reported that higher carbonation has been found in concrete containing fly ash. Contrary to these studies, in a case, where a 25-year-old fly ash foundation concrete was examined, and it has been reported that there has been no carbonation in the fly ash concrete specimens.

The study by (Thomas et al. 1992), concludes that concretes with up to 30% fly ash carbonated to a similar or slightly greater degree compared with OPC concretes of the same strength grade. However, concretes containing 50% fly ash carbonated at significantly greater rates. This study reports carbonation of fly ash concrete, with particular emphasis on the role of curing. It also observes that in some cases increasing the initial curing period from 1 to 7 days had the effect of reducing carbonation by 50%. Concretes with nominal strength grades M25, M35 and M4.5 and a range of fly ash levels (0-50%) were exposed to various treatments and environment during the first 28 days. After 28 days the concrete cubes were stored either internally or externally (sheltered) and the rate of carbonation was monitored.

Also, Papadakis (Papadakis et al. 2000) reported that in the case fly ash is introduced as a fine aggregate replacement, the carbonation rate is reduced. However, reaction products between pozzolanic silica and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ result in the denser structure of the HCP, so diffusivity is reduced, and carbonation is likely to be slowed down. For this to happen, good curing is essential (Parrott et al. 1987; Hobbs et al. 1988)

4.2 Carbonation of Concrete Containing Silica Fume

A study by (Kulakowski et al. 2009) signifies the conclusions regarding the depth of carbonation, carbonation induced reinforcement corrosion in concrete samples with silica fume addition up to 20%, and the water/binder ratios ranging from 0.30-0.80. The water-binder ratios specify the behaviors of the additions. In the materials having w/b ratios lower or equal to 0.45-0.50, the porosity of the material is the governing factor in the process of carbonation whereas the consumption of the calcium hydroxide has an insignificant effect on the carbonation. On the contrary for higher w/b ratios, a substantial role is played by the consumption of calcium hydroxide. At the same time, the results concluded from the reinforcement corrosion studies, direct that the outcome of the silica fume addition is to be governed by their concentration. Silica fume will not lessen the corrosion resistance for the concentrations equal to or lower than 10%, and it might increase it when used in the concentrations below this level. Silica fume increases the potential for carbonation-induced reinforcement corrosion when used in the concentrations greater than 10%.

5. EFFECTS OF WATER/CEMENT RATIO

The water/cement (w/c) and water/binder ratio are considered as one of the most important design parameters affecting the concrete quality. It has been verified by several studies that depth of carbonation increases with increase in water/cement ratio. This is attributed to the strong influence of w/c ratio on microstructural properties of concrete. The effect of the water-cement ratio of cement pastes on microstructural characteristics related to carbonation process was studied in (T. Chaussadent H. Hornain, N. Rafai, and A. Ammouche et al. 2000). Investigations were performed during the hydration process at an early age and on 28-day and 2-year-old hydrated cement pastes. The mix was made with a Type I Normal Portland Cement. The w/c ratios used in this study were 0.25, 0.35, 0.45, and 0.60. It was observed that the microstructural characteristics are very different between pastes having w/c values above 0.35-0.40 and below 0.35-0.40. When w/c is more than this value, the porosity strongly increases, and the calcium hydroxide appears in large crystals. It was also observed that, for an equivalent degree of hydration, the calcium hydroxide amount increases and the CaO /SiO₂ ratio of the C – S – H decreases as the w/c increases.

An experimental study by (Roy et al. 1999) to understand the effect of water-cement ratio on carbonation has been conducted, using w/c ratios of 0.55, 0.60, 0.65, 0.70 and 0.75. The cubes were cast, and their compressive strength was measured after 28 days of curing, another prism cast of the same sample was cured for 7 days and transferred to the carbonation chamber and their carbonation depths were measured weekly, for 6 weeks. The data of carbonation depth are summarized in Table.6 It has been observed that samples having higher w/c ratios, i.e. the ratios, which are of a lower grade of concrete shows larger carbonation depths. The rate constants, K (mm/year^{0.5}) were calculated on the basis of carbonation depths, assuming carbonation is a diffusion-controlled phenomenon and the carbonation depth d (in mm), is correlated to the exposure time, t (years) by the equation:

$$d = K t^{0.5}$$

The calculated K-values are shown in Table 6: it has been observed that K increases with increasing w/c ratio or decreasing cube strength. Similar relationship between concrete strength (grade, quality) and carbonation rate has been quite well established in several previous studies.

It was concluded that there exists a relationship between the rate (depth) of carbonation and the strength of the concrete sample. The carbonation depth was found to be proportional to (strength)⁻¹ and the carbonation rate constants, K (mm year)^{0.5} measured in the accelerated laboratory tests are significantly higher than those found in normal atmospheric conditions.

Similar results were also obtained in the study by (Fattuhi et al. 1986). Accelerated carbonation technique used to investigate the effects of concrete mix w/c ratio on the rate of concrete carbonation. Prisms 50 x 50 x 285 mm made from concretes with w/c ratios of 0.7, 0.6 or 0.4. The prisms were initially water cured for 1, 3, 7, 21 or 28 days; then they were placed in a chamber filled with CO₂ gas. The carbonation depth was examined using phenolphthalein indicator. The results showed that the depth of carbonation increased with increase in the concrete w/c ratio.

5.1 Effect of Ambient Humidity and Moisture Content

Deterioration of the concrete may be caused by various chemical processes, and water may act as an essential component in these reactions. For lower relative humidity (RH less than 50%), diffusion of CO₂ into concrete is high, but there may not be enough water in the pores to support carbonation. For a high RH, diffusion of CO₂ is very low, which leads to a reduction in carbonation and its carbonation rate. That is why the majority of the studies on concrete carbonation use RH between 50% and 70%.

Roy (Roy et al. 1999) conducted an experimental study to find the effect of humidity levels on the depth of carbonation, the author used five different grades of concrete (grade 20, 25, 30, 35 and 40 with w/c ratio of 0.8, 0.7, 0.65, 0.6 and 0.55 respectively). After curing for 28 days, the samples were transferred in special chambers having CO₂ at 6% by volume with humidity levels 52, 64, 75, 84 and 92%, to accelerate the carbonation process. Carbonation tests were carried out at five different exposure periods viz. 0, 1, 4, 8 and 16 weeks.

From Fig. 4, it is visible that significant carbonation is visible only after 8 or 16 weeks. By looking at the carbonation depth v/s humidity level relationship after 16 weeks exposure, the same general trends can be seen from all five grades of concrete. As the humidity level increases from 52 to 75%, there is a significant increase in carbonation depth with increasing humidity level. There is then a decrease in carbonation depth as the relative humidity increases from 75 to 84% before the carbonation depth increases once again as the relative humidity increases to 92%.

Fig. 4: Carbonation depth v/s humidity level for different grades of concrete (Roy et al. 1999)

Several factors significantly influence the rate and depth of carbonation:

Table 6: Cube Strength, Carbonation Depths and Carbonation Rate Constants K, for the Grades of Concrete

Water/cement ratio	Cube strength (Mpa)	Carbonation depth (mm) after different exposure periods						Carbonation rate constant K (mm/year ^{-0.5})
		7	14	21	28	35	42	
0.55	27.0	0	1	2.2	3.0	3.7	5.3	10.89
0.60	26.5	0	1	2.8	3.3	4.5	5.5	11.89
0.65	23.5	0	1	3.3	3.8	5.1	7.1	13.7
0.70	20.5	0	1	3.9	4.3	6.1	7.5	15.5
0.75	18.5	0	1	4.1	4.7	6.3	8.5	16.9

Table 7: Details of mix used in (Russell et al. 2001) (NOTE: Fine aggregate/course aggregate ratio held constant at 0.55)

Mix no.	w/c ratio	Cement content kg m ⁻³	Water content kg m ⁻³	Fine aggregate content kg m ⁻³	Course aggregate content kg m ⁻³	Achieved a/c ratio
1	0.50	375	192	685	1243	5.14
2	0.57	375	215	664	1207	4.99
3	0.63	375	234	647	1174	4.86
4	0.70	375	256	625	1140	4.71
5	0.50	315	164	732	1329	6.54
6	0.57	315	184	711	1296	6.37
7	0.63	315	201	696	1296	6.23
8	0.70	315	220	679	1233	6.07

So, based on the experimental study, it can be concluded that the effects of RH were complex with maxima being measured at both 75% and 92% RH. The former maxima are similar to real structures and the enhanced carbonation at latter maxima RH may be possible due to the difference in the mechanism(s) of carbonation in the accelerated depths (Roy et al. 1999).

Author, (Russell et al. 2001) conducted a study to investigate the effect of relative humidity on the rate of carbonation. Based on data from an accelerated carbonation test, descriptive models were developed to quantify the effects of the relative humidity on the rate of carbonation. Eight different concrete mixes were used. Four different w/c ratios and two cement contents (CC) were used. Three batches of these eight mixes were cast for testing at three different RH conditions: 55, 65 and 75% RH. All other properties like curing, conditioning and exposure to the CO₂ environment was held constants for all mixes. Details of the eight mixes used in the test are given in Table 7. Class 42.5N Portland cement (OPC) conforming to BS12: 1991(BS12: 1991) was used. The carbonation chamber was set to maintain a 5% CO₂ (±0.5%) concentration at 20°C (±1°C) during the testing. Carbonation was measured using 1% phenolphthalein solution. Internal humidity was monitored at 0, 10, 20, 30- and 40-mm depths from the exposed surface.

The rates of carbonation of all mixes are given in Table 8 using the equation 22. The overall trend observed is that rate of carbonation decreases with increasing RH. For the lower w/c ratio mixes, the greatest change in the rate of carbonation occurred between 55% and 65% target RH. Maximum carbonation occurred at 55–65% RH. From 65 to 75% RH there was a decrease in the rate of carbonation.

Table 8: Carbonation rates obtained for different values of RH in (Russell et al. 2001)

w/c ratio	Cement content kg m ⁻³	Target relative humidity		
		55%	65%	75%
		Carbonation rate mm/(week ^{0.5})		
0.50	375	3.32	1.43	1.97
0.57	375	5.56	2.90	2.39
0.63	375	5.49	6.08	3.06
0.70	375	9.84	7.94	2.74
0.50	315	4.40	1.71	1.32
0.57	315	4.48	4.20	2.42
0.63	315	8.72	6.34	2.82
0.70	315	10.96	7.62	4.18

Pore Structure: Concrete with a denser pore structure can hinder CO₂ penetration, impacting carbonation depth.

6 . PRACTICAL APPLICATIONS OF ACCELERATED CARBONATION TECHNIQUES

6.1 Evaluation of Techniques

This section can be expanded to include a detailed analysis of various accelerated carbonation methods:

- **Pressurized Carbonation:** Involves injecting CO₂ under pressure (0.1 to 5 bars) for enhanced carbonation efficiency. However, this technique requires specialized equipment and may negatively impact concrete strength if not controlled properly.
- **Cyclic Pressurized Carbonation:** This method alternates between pressurized CO₂ injection and atmospheric pressure, potentially improving gas exchange and moisture management.
- **Deep Breathing Analogy (DBA):** Inspired by human lung mechanics, DBA utilizes alternating positive and negative pressures for enhanced CO₂ absorption. Further research is needed to assess its large-scale feasibility.

6.2 Additives and Curing Regimes

The use of specific additives can be explored further:

- **Fly Ash:** Replacing conventional cement with fly ash can improve compressive strength while facilitating CO₂ uptake in carbonated concrete. However, fly ash concrete may have lower early strength compared to ordinary Portland cement (OPC) mixes.
- **Novel Additives:** Recent research suggests the potential of specific additives in transforming concrete into effective carbon sinks without compromising mechanical properties. Further investigation is needed to validate their long-term performance.

7. DURABILITY AND PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT

7.1 Mechanical Properties

Accelerated carbonation can influence the mechanical properties of concrete in both positive and negative ways:

- *Compressive Strength*: Studies indicate potential increases in compressive strength, with improvements reported up to 111% depending on the mix design.
- *Flexural Strength*: Limited research suggests that accelerated carbonation might have a minimal impact or even slightly decrease flexural strength.
- *Bond Strength*: The potential impact of carbonation on bond strength between concrete and reinforcement requires further investigation.

7.2 Long-term Durability and Corrosion Resistance

Long-term studies are crucial to evaluate the durability of carbonated concrete:

- *Corrosion Resistance*: While carbonation can lead to a reduction in pH, controlled processes can mitigate risks associated with steel reinforcement corrosion by maintaining adequate alkalinity levels. However, prolonged exposure to aggressive environments, such as those containing chlorides or sulfates, could still compromise the durability of carbonated concrete.
- *Alkali-Silica Reaction (ASR)*: Accelerated carbonation can potentially reduce the risk of ASR by lowering the concrete's pH. However, further research is needed to confirm this effect in various aggregate types and under different environmental conditions.
- *Alkali-Silica Reaction (ASR)*: Accelerated carbonation can potentially reduce the risk of ASR by lowering the concrete's pH. However, further research is needed to confirm this effect in various aggregate types.
- *Chloride Ingress*: The potential impact of carbonation on chloride penetration resistance requires careful evaluation, particularly in structures exposed to de-icing salts. While carbonation can reduce the permeability of concrete, it's essential to consider the overall exposure conditions and the type of chlorides present.

8. ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT AND SUSTAINABILITY

8.1 Carbon Sequestration Potential

Utilizing concrete as a carbon sink could potentially capture up to two gigatons of CO₂ annually, significantly offsetting emissions from cement production. The controlled application of accelerated carbonation could enhance this potential by ensuring effective CO₂ absorption during the curing process. However, the long-term stability of carbonated concrete and the potential for CO₂ re-emission under certain conditions need further investigation.

8.2 Sustainable Construction Practices

Incorporating carbonated concrete into construction practices aligns with sustainability goals by reducing greenhouse gas emissions and improving material performance. The use of recycled concrete aggregates (RCA) treated through accelerated carbonation presents additional environmental benefits by reducing waste and enhancing material properties. However, the availability and quality of RCA can vary significantly, and careful consideration is needed to ensure the long-term performance of RCA-based concrete.

9. CONCLUSION

Accelerated carbonation represents a promising strategy for enhancing the sustainability of concrete structures and mitigating CO₂ emissions. By optimizing various techniques and understanding their impact on mechanical properties, durability, and environmental performance, the construction industry can leverage this process to create more sustain-

able and resilient infrastructure. However, further research is needed to address the long-term performance, environmental impact, and economic feasibility of accelerated carbonation at a larger scale. Carbonation is a multivariable and nonlinear phenomenon. The factors influencing carbonation of concrete are interdependent, and the entire process is highly complex. Thus, modelling for prediction of concrete carbonation should be based on nonlinear scheme. Nonlinear FEM based models performed satisfactorily for carbonation depth prediction. Several neural network-based models have also been developed. Because of nonlinear and interdependent nature of the problem ANN, GA and other artificial intelligence-based models can be deployed effectively.

In general, carbonation of concrete causes the increase in the thermal conductivity and all mechanical properties of concrete like strength, modulus of elasticity, and shrinkage of the concrete. Higher porosity gives rise to higher carbonation depths. To ensure lower porosity or denser structure, concrete should be uniform, well compacted and has high cement content.

Carbonation causes a reduction in porosity of the concrete. Therefore, carbonation slows down with time or its propagation. Pore blocking due to rain may also influence carbonation propagation

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